

DIGITAL SKILLS AUSTRIA 2022

THE DIGITAL SKILLS LADDER

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Digital Skills Austria 2022: Key Insights in English

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DISCLAIMER: This is a short English language overview of the study – the complete report in German can be accessed via the following source:

Grünangerl, M., & Prandner, D. (2022). *Digital Skills Austria 2022*. RTR -Rundfunk und Telekom Regulierungs-GmbH.

1. Study Background

The *Digital Skills Austria 2022* study focuses on the extent to which Austrians are able to navigate, communicate and even shape the digital space. The following document provides a brief insight into the key result of the study – the *Digital Skills Ladder*.

2. Methodology and the Digital Skills Scale

For the purpose of the study, a total of 2183 people from the Austrian online population aged 16 and over were surveyed in May 2022 on how they assess their digital skills (Online Access Panel, provided by the field agency of Marketagent). Quote sampling was used to create a sample that matches the structure of the Austrian online population age 16 and up in regard to age, sex and education. The composition of the sample can be seen the following table 1.

Analysis weights were calculated and applied for analysis.

DISCLAIMER: For more information about Marketagent and their services, please visit their official website at <http://www.marketagent.com/en>.

The fieldwork agency is ISO accredited. However, any work carried out using non-probabilistic sampling from a pre-selected access panel must be classified as structural matching and cannot be considered statistically representative of the population. Results must be read with appropriate caution.

Indicator	Value (mean or percentage)
Age (average)	46 Years
14 – 30	24%
31 – 45	26%
46 – 65	33%
65 +	17%
Max. Secondary I (no Matura)	68%
Secondary II (Matura or equal)	19%
Tertiary (Univ. or equal)	11%
Male	49%
Female	51%

Table 1 - Sample Composition, not weighted (n=2183)

The questionnaire used in the *Digital Skills Austria 2022* study is based on established, internationally tested measurement instruments. At the centre of the questionnaire are **39 items**, which were originally designed by Alexander van Deursen and Ellen Helsper as well as several colleagues of them (e.g. van Deursen et al., 2016, 2017; Helsper et al. 2021). Those questions are meant to map a four-dimensional structure of digital skills:

- (a) Technical and Operational Skills
- (b) Information Navigation and Processing
- (c) Communication and Interaction
- (d) Content Creation and Production

While the questionnaire for the *Digital Skills Austria* was using a German language translation of the items, the English language versions of the items used can be found in a recent publication by Helsper et al. from 2021 (esp. pp. 16 and 12). This document was the source of the original items dealing with digital skills. The responses were accompanied by a 5-point Likert scale. These range from very true, mostly true, neither true or untrue, not very true, to not true at all.

3. Results

The key results of Digital Skills Austria 2022 are the identification of the hierarchical structure of digital skills and the chance to organise them into a ladder with five different levels.

The **floor of the ladder (level 0)** represents individuals who have no mentionable skills in any of the four dimensions. At level 1 of the ladder, individuals already show the technical and operational skills (**level 1 of the ladder: application**) necessary to navigate the digital space. At level 2, additional skills for information navigating and processing information (**level 2 of the ladder: orientation**) are mastered. Individuals at the third level also show the ability to exchange information, which involves communication and interaction skills (**level 3 of the ladder: communication**). Finally, the highest level of the digital skills ladder encompasses all the previous dimensions and adds skills related to content creation and production (**level 4 of the ladder: production**).

To statistically confirm the existence of such a sequence, we tested if the items follow the logic of a so-called Guttman scale (cf. Andrich, 1985). Accordingly, we asked our respondents to assess their digital skills as follows: application, orientation, communication, and production. The ratio for this structure is, that someone will only be able to produce digital content if he or she can demonstrate all the skills that precede this level. The same applies to communication skills. You can only have communicative skills if you have also acquired application and orientation skills. The other levels work in the same way.

The actual construction and testing of the digital skills ladder was divided into several steps different. First, four so-called **latent factor variables** representing the four core dimensions were derived from the 38¹ original variables via exploratory factor analysis (for results see table 2). These latent variables were then dichotomised into two groups each: Those that expressed (very) high skill levels at a certain skill dimension and those who did not. Afterwards the Guttman procedure was used to determine whether they can be put in the order of the proposed ladder. The results of this were highly promising, showing that more than 93% of the sample could be mapped to the *Digital Skills Ladder*.²

<i>Skill dimension (number of cases)</i>	<i># items</i>	<i>Reliability (Cronbach's Alpha)</i>	<i>Extracted variance</i>	<i>KMO score</i>
technical and operational (n=2194)	10	0.931	62 %	0.955
information navigation and organisation (n=2237)	9	0.919	61 %	0.947
communication and interaction (n=2107)	10	0.926	60 %	0.956
content creation and production (n=2070)	9	0.937	61 %	0.918

Table 2 - Digital Skills Dimensions - reliability

¹ One variable of the scale – tied to coding – was excluded in accordance with the literature.

² Lowinger reproduction coefficient: 0.943; Goodenough & Edwards reproduction coefficient: 0.933. A reproduction coefficient of 0.9 required for Guttman scaling is thus exceeded (Bacher, 1990).

The Digital Skills Ladder | Scale: Level 0: Insufficient Skills

Key Indicators for Level 0

76 % without
Matura

€ 1450 (Median)

Ø 50 years
21 % up to 30 y.
24 % 66+

49% 51 %

The Digital Skills Ladder | Scale: Scale: Level 1: Basic technical skills

Key Indicators for Level 1

¼ with Matura

€ 1800 (Median)

Ø 55 years
4 out of 10 up to
65 Y.
⅓ 66+

49% 51 %

The Digital Skills Ladder | Scale: Level 2: Orientation Skills

Searching, finding and processing digitally available information is guaranteed at this level. People can orientate themselves in the digital space, find their way around websites and assess the information they find in terms of its usefulness, reliability and trustworthiness.

Key Indicators for Level 2:

28 % with Matura

€ 2250 (Median)

Ø 50 years

29% 71 %

The Digital Skills Ladder | Scale: Level 3: Communication Skills

Key Indicators for Level 3:

72 % without
matura
13 % univ. edu

€ 1800 (Median)

Ø 49 years
31 % up to 45 y.
44 % up to 65 y

55% 45 %

The Digital Skills Ladder | Scale: Level 4: Creation Skills

Key Indicators for Level 4:

19 % univ. edu

€ 1800 (Median)

Ø 42 years
28 % up to 30 y.
58 % up to 45 y.
11 % 66+

45% 55 %

Digital Skills and the Austrian Online Population

Approx. 94 % of the survey participants could be mapped to the stairway: Gutman Scaling (Reproduction coefficients: Lowinger: 0,943; Goodenough & Edwards: 0,933)

4. References

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